

Carbon Skeleton Synthesis on a Triosmium Cluster Framework: Preparation and Characterisation of a Triosmium Cluster containing a Long Chain of Seven Carbon Atoms : Crystal and Molecular Structure of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_7(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{C}_2)$

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The organometallic clusters $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9\text{P}(\text{OMe})_3(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2)$ (2), $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{RC}_2\text{R}')$ ($\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{H}$ (4), Me (5), Ph (6) $\text{R}=\text{Ph}$ $\text{R}'=\text{Me}$ (7)), are known and their structures have been established by a single-crystal X-ray studies. ^{13}C nmr spectral studies have now been carried out on these complexes in order to study their structures in solution. The mechanism for the formation of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{RC}_2\text{R}')$ from the reaction of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2)$ with $\text{RC}_2\text{R}'$ is discussed. The reactivity of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{RC}_2\text{R}')$ with nucleophiles such as Me, NO, H has also been examined. Reaction of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{RC}_2\text{R}')$ with one molar equivalent of Me, NO in the presence of MeCN results in the simple substitution of a carbonyl ligand by MeCN ligand to produce $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{RC}_2\text{R}')$ ($\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{H}$ (9) Ph (10); $\text{R}=\text{Ph}$, $\text{R}'=\text{Me}$ (11)). The addition of super hydride (H^-) to a solution of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{C}_2)$ results in the formation of an unstable formyl complex $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{CHO})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{C}_2)^-$, which upon protonation with $\text{HBF}_4 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ in the presence of MeCN yields $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_7(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{C}_2)$ (10). The structure of complex 9 has been established by single crystal analysis. The overall structure closely resembles that of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{Ph}_2)$ (6) with the $\mu_3\text{-}\eta^3$, η^4 -organic capping the scalene triosmium triangle. The acetonitrile replaces an axial carbonyl ligand on one of the osmium atoms.

The reactions of transition metal carbonyl clusters with alkynes have drawn considerable attention during recent years¹⁻¹⁰. We have been interested in exploring the chemistry of osmium carbonyl clusters with nuclearity ranging from three to seven with alkynes. The idea is to see if the increase in nuclearity produces any change in the reactivity and bonding capability of the bound alkyne fragment. Our research efforts have also been directed in introducing more than one alkyne ligand on a given cluster. We have been successful in introducing up to three alkyne ligands on a triosmium cluster which serves as a precursor to an osmacyclic derivative⁵. An osmacyclic ring arises from the coupling of two alkyne ligands. The coupling of alkynes sometimes accompanied by the uptake of a carbonyl ligand. For example, the cluster $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2)$ (1) contains an osmacyclopentadienone ring arises from the linking of a carbonyl and two dimethylacetylene ligands¹⁻¹¹, to form a chain of five carbon atoms. We were interested to see if we can make this carbon chain longer by introducing another alkyne ligand(s). In this paper we report the synthesis, reactivity and ^{13}C nmr spectral analysis of three types of cluster derivative, viz. $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9\text{P}(\text{OMe})_3(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2)$, $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{R}_2\text{C}_2)$ and $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_7(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{R}_2\text{C}_2)$ containing long chains of five or seven carbon atoms. The molecular structures of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9\text{P}(\text{OMe})_3(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2)$ (2)

and $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{C}_2)$ (6) have already been reported briefly¹, and we now report the crystal and molecular structure of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_7(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{Ph}_2\text{C}_2)$.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of $\text{H}_2\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}$ or $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2$ with Me_2C_2 yields a red cluster with a formulation $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2)$ (1)^{1,11}. The ^1H nmr spectrum of 1 shows two equal intensity singlet resonances at δ 3.29 and 2.37 due to two pairs of inequivalent methyl groups¹¹. The signal at δ 2.37, being the most shielded, is assigned to the $\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{C}(\text{O})$ groups, whereas the other at δ 3.29, is assigned to $\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{C}(\text{O})\text{C}(\text{Me})$ groups. The ir spectrum of 1 displays a broad band at 1616 cm^{-1} in addition to bands in the terminal carbonyl region¹¹. On the basis of spectroscopic data, Deeming has proposed a structure (Fig 1) containing an osmacyclopentadienone ring¹¹. No crystal structure of this compound has been reported so far. We have not been able to grow X-ray quality crystals of 1, but have studied the variable temperature ^{13}C nmr spectrum and found that our data is fully consistent with the proposed structure. Additional evidence to support this structure comes from the crystal structure of its phosphite derivative, $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9\text{P}(\text{OMe})_3(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2)$ (2). The structure of 2 has previously been discussed¹ and is similar

Fig. 1. Proposed structure of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2)$ (1).

to that proposed for the parent cluster 1 with one of the carbonyl ligands replaced by $\text{P}(\text{OMe})_3$ ligand.

^{13}C nmr study on 1: ^{13}C nmr studies have been carried out on an enriched (^{13}CO) sample of 1, which in turn was prepared starting from $\text{Os}_3-(^{13}\text{CO})_{10}(\text{NCMe})_2$ (ca. 40% ^{13}C). The alkyne carbons are located at δ 161.9 and 80.9. A large difference in the chemical shifts reflects different deshielding effects experienced by these nuclei. The resonance at δ 161.9, being the most deshielded, is assigned to the $\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{C}(\text{O})$ nucleus, whereas the other at δ 80.9 is assigned to $\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{C}(\text{O})$ nucleus. A similar observation is noticed by Hart and coworkers in the complex $\text{WCo}(\text{CO})_7\{\text{C}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Me}-4)\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{C}(\text{O})\}^{12}$.

The carbonyl ligands in the complex 1 are fluxional in solution at room temperature. The mobility of the carbonyl ligands can be suppressed by cooling the sample to 243 K. At this temperature, the spectrum exhibits six carbonyl singlet resonances at δ 183.0, 179.5, 179.3, 176.9, 172.5 and 169.8 with an intensity ratio of 1 : 2 : 2 : 1 : 2 : 2 (Fig. 2) and is consistent with the structure proposed earlier by Deeming¹¹. Low intensity satellites arising from ^{187}Os coupling (at the natural abundance level, 1.64%, $I=1/2$) were also observed in the ^{13}C nmr spectrum of 1. The various nuclear spin-spin coupling constants $\{^1J(^{187}\text{Os}-^{13}\text{C})\}$ are recorded in Table 1, together with their probable assignments. The low-field resonance at δ 183.0 is straightforwardly assigned to the keto-carbon labelled as a. The resonances at δ 169.8 and 176.9 remain sharp at room temperature and have been assigned to the carbonyl ligands bonded to an osmium atom where the organic ligand form σ -bonds. The former resonance with a small coupling to ^{187}Os ($^1J(^{187}\text{Os}-^{13}\text{C})=87 \pm 2$ Hz) is assigned to the two carbonyls *trans* to the (formally) σ -bonded organic ligand whereas the latter resonance with somewhat larger coupling ($^1J(^{187}\text{Os}-^{13}\text{C})=122 \pm 2$ Hz) is unambiguously assigned to carbonyl ligand labelled as b. We are unable to make any further assignments based on the data available and the assignments shown in Fig. 2 are arbitrary.

Fig. 2. ^{13}C nmr spectra of $\text{Os}_3(^{13}\text{CO})_9(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2^{13}\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2)$ (1) recorded at different temperatures.

TABLE 1 NUCLEAR SPIN-SPIN COUPLING CONSTANTS $\{^1J(^{187}\text{Os}-^{13}\text{C})\}$ OF SOME NEW ORGANOMETALLIC CLUSTERS

Compd. no.	Chemical shift δ	Assignment of carbonyl ligands	$^1J(^{187}\text{Os}-^{13}\text{C})$ (± 2) Hz
1	179.5	d	109
	179.3	e	—
	176.9	b	122
	172.5	f	122
	169.8	c	87
	184.9		103
6	183.0		109
	182.0		—
	177.8		115
	175.7		—
	175.3		113
	171.6		92
9	170.0		114
	188.5		108
	183.8		120
	180.0		114
	178.5		116
	178.0		93
	176.4		97
	172.0		118

As the temperature is increased from 243 to 298 K, the resonances due to CO_{d,e,f} start broadening whereas the resonances due to CO_a and CO_b remain sharp. At higher temperatures ca. 333 K, an average signal due to the carbonyl ligands labelled as d, e, f centered at δ 177.86 is visible and overlaps with the resonance due to CO_b thereby suggesting a localised scrambling of carbonyl ligands d, e, f. Decomposition of the sample occurs on further heating.

Chemistry of Os₃(CO)₉(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) (1) :
It is known that the cluster Os₃(CO)₉(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) (1) in refluxing heptane breaks down to a dinuclear complex Os₂(CO)₆(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂)¹¹. In order to study the substitution chemistry of 1 with other donor ligands, we have chemically activated the complex 1 with Me₃NO/MeCN. Reaction of 1 with Me₃NO in the presence of MeCN affords the activated complex Os₃(CO)₈(NCMe)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) 3. The ir spectrum of 3 displays a strong band at 1 606 cm⁻¹ due to a keto group, thereby indicating that an osmacyclopentadienone ring is retained¹. No molecular ion peak is observed in an electron impact mass spectrum, the highest peak observed corresponds to the formulation 'Os₃(CO)₈(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂)'. Based on formal electron counting rules, the carbonyl ligands associated with two different osmium atoms in 1 would be equally susceptible towards nucleophilic attack by amine-oxide. Experience in this laboratory suggests that the carbonyl ligands attached to an osmium atom bearing a σ -bonded acetylenic carbon are more electron positive than the carbonyl ligands attached to an osmium atom bearing a π -bonded acetylenic carbon^{5,12}, and is more susceptible to attack. Therefore, the cluster 3 should have a structure similar to that of the parent cluster 1 with one of the carbonyl ligands associated with an osmium atom bearing a σ -bonded acetylenic carbon replaced by an acetonitrile ligand. This prediction indeed was confirmed from the crystal structure of the phosphite derivative Os₃(CO)₈P(OMe)₃(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) (2) where the incoming phosphite ligand is attached with an osmium atom bearing a σ -bonded acetylenic carbon.

The acetonitrile ligand in 3 can be readily displaced by P(OMe)₃ to produce a substituted complex with the formulation Os₃(CO)₈P(OMe)₃(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) (2) in 60% yield. The ir spectrum of 2 in the terminal carbonyl region is very similar to that of 3, thereby indicating that a simple substitution of the acetonitrile by a P(OMe)₃ ligand has taken place¹. The ¹H nmr spectrum of 2 exhibits a doublet resonance at δ 3.65 (³J_{P-H} = 12.2 Hz) due to a coordinated P(OMe)₃ group. In addition to this, three methyl singlet resonances with an intensity ratio of 1 : 1 : 2 are also visible. The ³¹P{¹H} nmr spectrum of 2 shows a singlet resonance at δ -26.6 assigned to a coordinated P(OMe)₃ ligand. The structure of 2 was established crystallographically and has been reported previously¹.

¹³C nmr study of 2 : ¹³C nmr studies have been carried out on 2 which confirm that the solid state structure is maintained in solution. The room temperature ¹³C nmr spectrum of 2 displays a singlet resonance at δ 186.9 due to a ketonic carbon (labelled as a, Fig. 3) and a doublet resonance at δ 175.9 (²J_{P-C} = 10.1 Hz) due to carbonyl ligands labelled as b. A broad resonance at δ 181.2 is also

Fig. 3. ¹³C nmr spectrum of Os₃(CO)₈P(OMe)₃(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) (3) recorded at different temperatures.

visible, which may be taken to indicate that the remaining six carbonyl ligands are fluxional. It is apparent that the two carbonyl ligands (labelled as b) are not involved in the exchange process. On cooling the sample to 243 K, the fluxional process can be frozen out and the spectrum displays five resonances with an intensity ratio of 1 : 2 : 2 : 2 : 2 consistent with the solid state structure of 2 (Table 2).

No change in the spectrum was noticed when recorded at higher temperatures (ca. 353 K), thereby suggesting no internuclear exchange between carbonyl ligands labelled as b and c/d/e is occurring.

TABLE 2— ^{13}C NMR DATA OF NEW ORGANOMETALLIC CLUSTERS

Compd. no.	Temp. K	^{13}C chemical shifts and their assignments
1	243	183(s, 1CO), 179.5(s, 2CO), 179.3(s, 2CO), 176.9(s, 1CO), 172.5(s, 2CO), 169.8(s, 2CO), 161.9(s, 2C), 80.9(s, 2C)
2	243	186.9(s, 1CO), 180.7(s, 1CO), 182.1(s, 1CO), 175.9(d, 1CO) $^3J_{\text{P-C}}=10.1$ Hz, 174.1(s, 1CO)
4	298	203.9(s, 1CO), 184.9(s, 1CO), 183.0(s, 1CO), 182.0(s, 1CO), 177.8(s, 1CO), 175.7(s, 1CO), 175.3(s, 1CO), 171.6(s, 1CO), 170.0(s, 1CO), 133.1(s, 1C), 123.9(s, 1C), 102.6(s, 1C), 98.2(s, 1C), 96.1(s, 1C), 80.5(s, 1C)
9	298	205.2(s, 1CO), 188.5(s, 1CO), 183.8(s, 1CO), 180.0(s, 1CO), 178.5(s, 1CO), 178.0(s, 1CO), 178.4(s, 1CO), 173.9(s, 1CO), 172.0(s, 1CO), 132.0(s, 1C), 120.0(s, 1C), 98.6(s, 1C), 87.2(s, 1C), 87.9(s, 1C), 41.9(s, 1Me), 38.0(s, 1C), 32.0(s, 1Me), 28.7(s, 1Me), 19.2(s, 1Me), 5.0(s, 1Me)

Reaction of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{-C}_2)$ (3) with alkynes: The reactions of the activated complex 2 with alkynes were of interest to us, as it may insert into a formal metal-carbon bond of the metallacyclic ring to produce an even larger organic ligand on the cluster surface.

Reactions of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{-C}_2)$ (3) with alkynes, $\text{RC}_2\text{R}'$, afford an orange cluster with the formulation $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{RC}_2\text{R}')(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{-Me}_2\text{C}_2)$ { $\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{H}$ (4), Me (5), Ph (6); $\text{R}=\text{Ph}$, $\text{R}'=\text{Me}$ (7)} in 60–70% yield. The ir spectra of all these products are very similar and show a band at $\sim 1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$, consistent with the presence of a keto-group¹. The ^1H nmr spectrum of 5 displays six singlet resonances of equal intensity, indicating that all the six methyl groups are inequivalent¹. The ^1H nmr spectrum of 4 exhibits two doublet resonances at δ 8.84 and 6.65 with a $^3J_{\text{H-H}}$ of ca. 4.6 Hz which have been assigned to acetylenic hydrogens and four singlet resonances assigned to four inequivalent methyl groups. The resonance at δ 8.84, being the most deshielded, is assigned to the $\text{C}(\text{H})\text{C}(\text{H})\text{C}(\text{O})$ group, whereas the other at δ 6.65, is assigned to $\text{C}(\text{H})\text{C}(\text{H})\text{C}(\text{O})$ group. Furthermore, the ^1H nmr spectrum of 7 shows it to be a mixture of two isomers in the ratio of 4:1, which may result from the different orientation of the incoming asymmetrical alkyne (see structure later in the text). We have previously established the molecular geometry of these clusters by a single crystal X-ray diffraction experiment¹. The structure is based on a triangular arrangement of osmium atoms and the incoming alkyne ligand ($\text{RC}_2\text{R}'$) has inserted into one of the $\text{Os}-\text{C}$ bond of an osmacyclic ring to produce a large organic ligand consisting of seven carbon atoms. This organic ligand is bonded to the triosmium cluster unit via σ -, π - and π -allyl bonds.

The mechanism for the formation of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{-C}_2\text{RC}_2\text{R}')$ from the reaction of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{-C}_2)$ with $\text{RC}_2\text{R}'$ is still uncertain. However, it is believed that the initial step is the replacement of an acetonitrile ligand by an alkyne ligand to produce [A], where the incoming alkyne functions as a two electron donor ligand (Fig. 4). The intermediate species [A] has not been isolated or characterised but the corresponding ethylene derivative $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)(\text{Me}_2\text{-C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{-C}_2)$ (8) has been isolated and characterised on the basis of ir and mass spectroscopy (Table 3). Subsequent rearrangement of [A] via the formal insertion of an alkyne into an $\text{Os}-\text{C}$ bond of an osmacycle leads to the observed product (Fig. 4). Due to the known instability of the complex 8, its conversion to yield the derivative 4 could not be achieved experimentally.

Fig. 4. Proposed mechanism for the formation of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{-C}_2\text{RC}_2\text{R})$.

^{13}C nmr study on $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{-C}_2\text{-H}_2\text{C}_2)$ (4): Having established the geometry of these clusters, it is now easy to understand the ^{13}C nmr spectrum. The $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ nmr spectrum of 4, recorded at room temperature, exhibits nine sharp equal intensity singlet resonances due to carbonyl ligands at δ 203.9, 184.9, 183.0, 182.0, 177.8, 175.7, 175.3, 171.6 and 170.0 (Table 2). The low-field resonance at δ 203.9 is straightforwardly assigned to a ketonic carbon. We are unable to make any further assignments unambiguously. Low intensity satellites arising from ^{187}Os coupling in the ^{13}C nmr spectrum were also observed. The $^1J(^{187}\text{Os}-^{13}\text{C})$ are recorded in Table 1. In addition to the resonances due to carbonyl ligands, the spectrum exhibits six singlet resonances due to alkynic carbons at δ 133.1, 123.9, 102.6, 98.2, 96.1 and 80.5

TABLE 3—SPECTRAL DATA

Compd. no	ν_{CO}	Mass ^b	¹ H nmr ^c
8	2 081m, 2 043s, 2 020vs, 1 986m,br, 1 605w,br	964	—
9	2 060m, 2 027vs, 2 002vs, 1 967m, 1 955m, 1 931m, 1 606m	934 ^b	8 65(1H, d) 6.64(1H, d) ³ J _{H-H} =4.8 Hz 3.25(3H, s) 2.78(1H, s) 2.24(3H, s) 1.82(3H, s) 1.62(3H, s)
10	2 058m, 2 029vs, 1 998vs, 1 969m, 1 955m, 1 930m, 1 606m	1086 ^b	7.10(10H, m) 3.3(3H, s) 2.88(3H, s) 2.32(3H, s) 2.0(3H, s) 1 8(3H, s)
11	2 057m, 2 026vs, 2 000s, 1 961m, 1 952m, 1 931m, 1 610w,br	1024 ^b	7.45(5H, m) I 3.22(3H, s) 2 84(3H, s) 2.82(3H, s) 2 21(3H, s) 1.81(3H, s) II 3.28(3H, s) 2.78(3H, s) 2 2(3H, s) 2.12(3H, s) 1.78(3H, s) I : II :: 4 : 1

^aIn CH₂Cl₂. ^bParent peak not observed. ^cIn CD₂Cl₂.

(Table 2). In the ¹H coupled ¹³C nmr spectrum, the resonance at δ 123.9 appears as a doublet with ¹J_{C-H}=164.5 Hz whereas the other resonance at δ 98.2 appears as a doublet of doublets with ¹J_{C-H}=169.6 Hz; ³J_{C-H}=3.5 Hz and have been assigned to the C-H carbons of the organic ligand whereas the remaining four resonances δ 133.1, 102.6, 96.1 and 80.5 have been assigned to C-Me carbons of the organic ligand. The coupling constants (²J_{C-H}) indicate that the C-H carbons are *sp*²-hybridised. Furthermore, the resonance at δ 123.9, being the most deshielded, is assigned to the C-H carbon of the organic ligand which forms a σ - and a π -allyl bond whereas the other at δ 98.2 is assigned to the other C-H carbon of the organic ligand which forms only a π -allyl bond.

The appearance of sharp resonances due to carbonyl ligands at room temperature indicates that the carbonyl ligands are not fluxional. The fluxionality of the carbonyl ligands in the complex 4 have been examined at higher temperatures. As the temperature is increased (ca. 323 K), the resonances at δ 183.0, 175.7 and 170.0 start broadening and finally collapse at 353 K. The other six resonances remain sharp even up to 373 K. It is believed that the carbonyl ligands labelled as d, e, f associated with an osmium atom to which the organic ligand form σ -bonds are fluxional (localised motion) whereas the other carbonyl ligands remain static. This is consistent with our previous observation that the carbonyl ligands associated with an osmium atom to which the alkyne form σ -bonds possess a lower

activation energy relative to the carbonyl ligands associated with the osmium to which the alkyne forms a π -bond¹³.

Reactivity of Os₃(CO)₈(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂RC₂R'): The reactivity of the cluster Os₃(CO)₈(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂RC₂R') with various other nucleophiles is also examined. The cluster Os₃(CO)₈(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂RC₂R') (R=R'=H (3), Ph (5); R=Ph, R'=Me (6)) reacts with Me₃NO in the presence of MeCN to produce a yellowish orange cluster with a formulation Os₃(CO)₇(NCMe)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂RC₂R') (R=R'=H (9), Ph (10); R=Ph, R'=Me (11)) in good yields. These clusters have been completely characterised by spectroscopic techniques (Table 3) and the structure of 9 established by X-ray analysis. These clusters can also be obtained from the reaction of Os₃(CO)₈(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂RC₂R') with H⁻/H⁺ though the conversion via this route is poor. The addition of one molar equivalent of super hydride (LiBEt₃H in THF) to a CH₂Cl₂ solution of 5 resulted in an immediate colour change from orange to dark orange. An ir spectrum of the resulting dark orange solution shows it to be anionic which reverts back to the starting cluster on standing in solution (10–15 min). The ir spectrum of the anionic cluster still shows a broad band in the 1 600 cm⁻¹ region thereby suggesting that the attack of the H⁻ has taken place either at an osmium atom or at one of the metal coordinated carbonyl ligand. The progress of the reaction was then monitored by ¹H nmr spectroscopy in order to determine the site of nucleophilic attack by H⁻. The reaction was repeated in a 5 mm nmr tube using deuterated THF (d₆) instead of CD₂Cl₂ as a solvent and ¹H nmr spectrum was run immediately on a WM250 nmr machine after the addition of super hydride. The ¹H nmr spectrum displays a singlet resonance at δ 11.99 apart from other methyl and phenyl resonances. No resonance in the metal hydride region (0 to -30 ppm) was observed. The appearance of a singlet resonance at δ 11.99 suggests that the attack of the H⁻ has taken place at one of the metal coordinated carbonyl ligands. On the basis of these results, this dark orange complex is formulated as Os₃(CO)₇-(CHO)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂Ph₂C₂)⁻ (12). The addition of HBF₄·Et₂O to a CH₂Cl₂/MeCN (15/2 cm³) solution of 12 results in a colour change from dark orange to yellowish orange. Work-up of the reaction mixture afforded a yellowish orange cluster 10 in about 20% yield. The other products of the reaction were not characterised.

In order to establish the geometry of these clusters and also to ascertain the exact location of the acetonitrile ligand a single crystal X-ray analysis of Os₃(CO)₇(NCMe)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂H₂C₂) (9) was undertaken. The crystal structure consists of discrete molecules separated by normal van der Waals distances. The molecular structure of 9 is shown in Fig. 5, while associated bond lengths and angles are presented in Tables 4 and 5, respectively. The three Os atoms lie at the vertices of

Fig. 5. The molecular structure of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_7(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{C}_2)$ (9).

TABLE 4—BOND LENGTHS (Å)

Os(1)–Os(2)	2.701 (1)	Os(1)–Os(3)	3.017 (1)
Os(1)–N(1)	2.082 (11)	Os(1)–C(3)	1.888 (15)
Os(1)–C(4)	1.873 (14)	Os(1)–C(15)	2.250 (12)
Os(1)–C(16)	2.177 (11)	Os(2)–Os(3)	2.801 (1)
Os(2)–C(8)	1.950 (15)	Os(2)–C(9)	1.870 (15)
Os(2)–C(10)	2.147 (12)	Os(2)–C(11)	2.235 (13)
Os(2)–C(12)	2.291 (12)	Os(2)–C(16)	2.067 (12)
Os(3)–C(5)	1.894 (15)	Os(3)–C(6)	1.909 (14)
Os(3)–C(7)	1.892 (12)	Os(3)–C(10)	2.165 (13)
Os(3)–C(13)	2.213 (11)	N(1)–C(1)	1.145 (18)
C(1)–C(2)	1.444 (22)	C(3)–O(1)	1.148 (20)
C(4)–O(2)	1.162 (17)	C(5)–O(3)	1.150 (19)
C(6)–O(4)	1.175 (17)	C(7)–O(5)	1.179 (15)
C(8)–O(6)	1.112 (19)	C(9)–O(7)	1.157 (19)
C(10)–C(11)	1.376 (17)	C(11)–C(12)	1.468 (18)
C(12)–C(13)	1.497 (17)	C(12)–C(17)	1.519 (17)
C(13)–C(14)	1.460 (17)	C(13)–C(18)	1.519 (19)
C(14)–C(15)	1.520 (18)	C(14)–O(8)	1.241 (15)
C(15)–C(16)	1.443 (18)	C(15)–C(19)	1.551 (18)
C(16)–C(20)	1.563 (18)		

a scalene triangle. Os (1) is coordinated to an axial acetonitrile ligand and to two terminal carbonyls in equatorial positions. Os (2) is coordinated to two terminal carbonyls, one in an axial and one in an equatorial site. Os (3) is coordinated to three terminal carbonyls, one in an axial site and two in equatorial sites. The acetonitrile ligand and all the carbonyl groups are essentially linear. The organic ligand forms a seven carbon atom chain, and is coordinated to the osmium triangle in a $\mu_3-\eta^2, \eta^4$ fashion, via three σ -, a π - and a π -allylic bond, in a manner similar to that found in $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_8(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{Ph}_2)$ (6)¹. This ligand formally acts as an eight-electron donor and the cluster as a whole obeys the Effective Atomic Number Rule with a formal count of 48 electrons.

The three Os–Os distances in 9 are very similar to the equivalent lengths in 6¹. The Os–C distances

and the C–C distances within the organic ligand also follow the same trends as in 6, there being no significant differences between the two sets of parameters at the 3 σ level. The Os–N (acetonitrile) distance in 9 is similar to the value of 2.074(23) Å for the equivalent $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_{11}(\text{NCMe})^{14}$.

¹H nmr study of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_7(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{C}_2)$ (9): The ¹H nmr spectrum of 9 displays two doublet resonances at δ 8.65 and 6.64 with ³J_{H–H} = 4.8 Hz attributed to C–H protons of the organic ligand. The former resonance, being most deshielded, is assigned to the C(H)C(H)C(Me) part of the organic ligand whereas the latter resonance is assigned to the C(H)C(H)C(Me) part of the organic ligand. In addition to this, the spectrum exhibits five more resonances in the 3.3–1.6 ppm region due to methyl protons (Table 3). The resonance at δ 2.24 may be assigned to the methyl protons of the coordinated acetonitrile ligand. The assignment of the remaining four singlet resonances to the particular methyl groups is difficult. The ¹H nmr data of these new complexes is given in Table 3.

¹³C nmr study of $\text{Os}_3(\text{CO})_7(\text{NCMe})(\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{Me}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_2\text{C}_2)$ (9): Having established the geometry of the cluster, it is now easy to understand the ¹³C nmr data. The ¹³C nmr spectrum of 9 measured at room temperature exhibits eight sharp singlet resonances due to carbonyl ligands in the range δ 205–172 (Table 2). The low field resonance at δ 205.2 is straightforwardly assigned to a ketonic carbon. We are unable to assign other resonances unambiguously. Low intensity satellites arising from ¹⁸⁷Os coupling in the ¹³C nmr spectrum were also observed and the corresponding ¹J(¹⁸⁷Os–¹³C) are recorded in Table 1. In addition to the resonances due to carbonyl ligands, the spectrum also displays singlet resonances at δ 173.9, 132.0, 120.0, 98.5, 87.2, 67.9, 41.9, 38.0, 32.0, 28.7, 19.2 and 5.0. In the ¹H coupled ¹³C nmr spectrum, the resonance at 120.0 appears as a doublet with ¹J_{C–H} = 163.5 Hz whereas the other resonance at δ 98.6 appears as a doublets of doublets with ¹J_{C–H} = 160.7 Hz; ²J_{C–H} = 3.3 Hz and have been assigned to the C–H carbon of the organic ligand which forms a σ - and a π -allyl bond whereas the other at δ 98.6 is assigned to the other C–H carbon of the organic ligand which forms only π -allyl bond. The resonance at δ 132.0 is assigned to the coordinated CH₃CN group as it shows a quartet with ²J_{C–H} of 10.7 Hz in the ¹H coupled ¹³C nmr spectrum. The resonances at δ 41.9, 32.0, 28.7 and 19.2 have been assigned to the methyl carbons as they exhibit distinct quartets (¹J_{C–H} ca. 127.7 Hz) in the ¹H coupled ¹³C nmr spectrum. The very high field resonance at δ 5.0 has been assigned to the methyl carbon of the coordinated acetonitrile group as it exhibits a quartet with ¹J_{C–H} of 138 Hz in the ¹H coupled ¹³C nmr spectrum. The remaining resonances at 173.9, 87.2, 67.9 and 38.0 which show unresolved multiplets in the ¹H coupled ¹³C nmr

TABLE 5—BOND ANGLES (°)

Os(3)—Os(1)—Os(2)	58.4(1)	N(1)—Os(1)—Os(2)	99.3(3)
N(1)—Os(1)—Os(3)	88.1(3)	C(3)—Os(1)—Os(2)	112.1(5)
C(3)—Os(1)—Os(3)	169.4(5)	C(3)—Os(1)—N(1)	89.1(5)
C(4)—Os(1)—Os(2)	154.6(4)	C(4)—Os(1)—Os(3)	100.7(4)
C(4)—Os(1)—N(1)	93.8(5)	C(4)—Os(1)—C(3)	89.6(6)
C(15)—Os(1)—Os(2)	76.2(3)	C(15)—Os(1)—Os(3)	82.5(3)
C(15)—Os(1)—N(1)	170.6(5)	C(15)—Os(1)—C(3)	100.3(6)
C(15)—Os(1)—C(4)	87.6(5)	C(16)—Os(1)—Os(2)	48.7(3)
C(16)—Os(1)—Os(3)	88.3(3)	C(16)—Os(1)—N(1)	142.7(4)
C(16)—Os(1)—C(3)	87.8(5)	C(16)—Os(1)—C(4)	123.5(5)
C(16)—Os(1)—C(15)	88.0(5)	Os(3)—Os(2)—Os(1)	66.5(1)
C(b)—Os(2)—Os(1)	86.0(4)	C(8)—Os(2)—Os(3)	95.9(4)
C(9)—Os(2)—Os(1)	126.2(5)	C(9)—Os(2)—Os(3)	167.2(5)
C(9)—Os(2)—C(8)	87.2(6)	C(10)—Os(2)—Os(1)	115.5(3)
C(10)—Os(2)—Os(3)	49.8(3)	C(10)—Os(2)—C(8)	91.0(5)
C(10)—Os(2)—C(9)	117.9(6)	C(11)—Os(2)—Os(1)	182.7(3)
C(11)—Os(2)—Os(3)	72.0(3)	C(11)—Os(2)—C(8)	120.4(5)
C(11)—Os(2)—C(9)	95.7(6)	C(11)—Os(2)—C(10)	36.5(5)
C(12)—Os(2)—Os(1)	105.0(3)	C(12)—Os(2)—Os(3)	70.6(3)
C(12)—Os(2)—C(8)	156.4(5)	C(12)—Os(2)—C(9)	102.0(5)
C(12)—Os(2)—C(10)	65.4(4)	C(12)—Os(2)—C(11)	37.8(5)
C(16)—Os(2)—Os(1)	52.3(3)	C(16)—Os(2)—Os(3)	96.7(3)
C(16)—Os(2)—C(8)	125.4(5)	C(16)—Os(2)—C(9)	91.6(6)
C(16)—Os(2)—C(10)	135.2(5)	C(16)—Os(2)—C(11)	114.0(5)
C(16)—Os(2)—C(12)	76.5(4)	Os(2)—Os(3)—Os(1)	55.2(1)
C(5)—Os(3)—Os(1)	171.5(4)	C(5)—Os(3)—Os(2)	132.3(4)
C(6)—Os(3)—Os(1)	89.6(4)	C(6)—Os(3)—Os(2)	98.9(4)
C(6)—Os(3)—C(5)	92.6(6)	C(7)—Os(3)—Os(1)	78.0(4)
C(7)—Os(3)—Os(2)	130.5(4)	C(7)—Os(3)—C(5)	93.6(6)
C(7)—Os(3)—C(6)	95.8(5)	C(10)—Os(3)—Os(1)	103.7(3)
C(10)—Os(3)—Os(2)	49.2(3)	C(10)—Os(3)—C(5)	84.3(5)
C(10)—Os(3)—C(6)	92.9(5)	C(10)—Os(3)—C(7)	171.2(5)
C(13)—Os(3)—Os(1)	86.7(3)	C(13)—Os(3)—Os(2)	71.6(3)
C(13)—Os(3)—C(5)	92.4(5)	C(13)—Os(3)—C(6)	170.2(5)
C(13)—Os(3)—C(7)	92.3(5)	C(13)—Os(3)—C(10)	79.2(4)
C(1)—N(1)—Os(1)	177.4(12)	C(2)—C(1)—N(1)	175.5(16)
O(1)—C(3)—Os(1)	178.6(14)	O(2)—C(4)—Os(1)	172.3(11)
O(3)—C(5)—Os(3)	178.1(13)	O(4)—C(6)—Os(3)	178.2(11)
O(5)—C(7)—Os(3)	176.6(11)	O(6)—C(8)—Os(2)	178.3(13)
O(7)—C(9)—Os(2)	178.1(14)	Os(3)—C(10)—Os(2)	81.0(4)
C(11)—C(10)—Os(2)	75.2(7)	C(11)—C(10)—Os(3)	113.7(9)
C(10)—C(11)—Os(2)	68.2(7)	C(12)—C(11)—Os(2)	73.2(7)
C(12)—C(11)—C(10)	115.1(11)	C(11)—C(12)—Os(2)	69.0(7)
C(13)—C(12)—Os(2)	101.3(8)	C(13)—C(12)—C(11)	113.8(10)
C(17)—C(12)—Os(2)	121.7(9)	C(17)—C(12)—C(11)	118.8(11)
C(17)—C(12)—C(13)	120.5(11)	C(12)—C(13)—Os(3)	104.8(8)
C(14)—C(13)—Os(3)	101.6(7)	C(14)—C(13)—C(12)	112.4(11)
C(18)—C(13)—Os(3)	116.2(8)	C(18)—C(13)—C(12)	112.1(10)
C(18)—C(13)—C(14)	109.3(10)	C(15)—C(14)—C(13)	122.8(11)
O(8)—C(14)—C(13)	122.4(11)	O(8)—C(14)—C(15)	114.8(11)
C(15)—C(15)—Os(1)	108.5(7)	C(16)—C(15)—Os(1)	68.3(6)
C(16)—C(15)—C(14)	119.8(11)	C(19)—C(15)—Os(1)	117.6(9)
C(19)—C(15)—C(14)	111.3(11)	C(19)—C(15)—C(16)	123.1(11)
Os(2)—C(16)—Os(1)	79.0(4)	C(15)—C(16)—Os(1)	73.8(6)
C(15)—C(16)—Os(2)	121.5(8)	C(20)—C(16)—Os(1)	122.4(9)
C(20)—C(16)—Os(2)	120.1(9)	C(20)—C(16)—C(15)	118.3(11)

spectrum due to long range C—H couplings have been assigned to the other alkyne carbons of the organic ligand. With the spectroscopic data available it is difficult to make any further assignments. It is interesting to note that the substitution of a carbonyl ligand in **4** by an acetonitrile ligand has produced a varied effect on the chemical shifts of the alkyne carbons of the organic ligand. The chemical shifts due to alkyne carbons of the cluster **4** fall in the range δ 133–80 while those in the acetonitrile derivative **9** fall in the range δ 173–38.

Reactivity of Os₃(CO)₇(NCMe)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂-C₃R₂C₂) (9): When an acetonitrile ligand is coor-

inated to a metal atom in a given cluster, it opens up a large scope for the substitution chemistry to be explored under relatively mild reaction conditions. Since the cluster Os₃(CO)₇(NCMe)(Me₂C₂-C(O)Me₂C₂R₂C₂) contains an acetonitrile ligand, it occurred to us that it could be a useful starting material to explore its substitution chemistry with other donor ligands and its reactions with phosphite and alkyne were thus investigated.

Room temperature stirring of **10** with P(OMe)₃ did not produce any change (by ir) and when the reaction was heated in toluene at 60° for 4 h, a number of products were observed by spot tlc in

very low yields and hence could not be completely characterised. Similarly, the reaction of 10 with alkyne was investigated with an aim to make the carbon chain longer, but no reaction was noticed at room temperature for 10 h. When the reaction mixture was heated in toluene at 80° for 5 h, very low yield of an uncharacterised neutral cluster was produced together with some uncharacterised anionic species. From these observations, we are forced to conclude that the acetonitrile ligand in these complexes is not very labile compared to other acetonitrile-osmium derivatives^{6,13,15,16}. The low lability of the acetonitrile ligand in these complexes is surprising, and the effect is thought to have an electronic origin.

Experimental

All syntheses were carried out under an inert atmosphere of dry N₂ unless otherwise stated. The complexes Os₃(CO)₉(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) (1), Os₃(CO)₈L(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) (L=P(OMe)₃ (2), MeCN (3)), Os₃(CO)₈(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂RC₂R') (R=R'=H (4), Me (5), Ph (6); R=Ph, R'=Me (7)) were synthesised by literature methods¹. The ¹³CO-enriched compounds were obtained from the ¹³CO-enriched Os₃(CO)₁₂ (ca. 40% ¹³C). The Me₃NO, as obtained commercially, was sublimed before use.

Proton, ¹³C and ³¹P nmr spectral data were obtained on Bruker WM250, WM400 spectrometers at 20° using deuteriated solvent as internal lock and reference (¹H: SiMe₄, δ=0; ³¹P: 85% H₃PO₄ in C₆D₆; δ=0; downfield positive), infrared spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer (2 200–1 600 cm⁻¹) and mass spectra on a AEI MS 12 spectrometer with ca. 70 eV (1.12 × 10⁻¹⁷J) ionising potential at 90–150°. Tris(perfluoroheptyl)-s-triazine was used as a reference.

Preparation of Os₃(CO)₇(NCMe)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂RC₂R') (R=R'=H (9), Ph (10); R=Ph, R'=Me (11)): The compound Os₃(CO)₈(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂RC₂R') (R=R'=H (4), Ph (6); R=Ph, R'=Me (7)) (50 mg) was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (25 cm³) and MeCN (3 cm³) was added to it. The contents of the reaction was stirred at -78° in a dry ice-acetone bath. A solution of Me₃NO (1.1 eq.) in CH₂Cl₂ (20 cm³) was added dropwise to the stirred suspension at -78° over a period of 0.5 h. The reaction mixture was gradually warmed to room temperature and left stirring for further 0.5 h. It was then filtered through silica to remove any unreacted amine-oxide. The solvent was then removed on a rotavap. Purification of the resulting reaction mixture by tlc (80% CH₂Cl₂ in hexane) produced a neutral orange band consisting of Os₃(CO)₇(NCMe)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂RC₂R') in 50% yield.

Reaction of Os₃(CO)₈(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂Ph₂C₂) with H⁻/H⁺: The cluster Os₃(CO)₈(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂Ph₂C₂) (25 mg) was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂/MeCN (15 cm³/2 cm³) and stirred at room temperature. To the stirred suspension one molar equivalent of super hydride (LiBEt₃H in THF) was added

dropwise over a period of 3–4 min which resulted in an immediate colour change for light orange to dark orange. The ir spectrum of the reaction mixture showed the formation of an anion which has been formulated as Os₃(CO)₇(CHO)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂Ph₂C₂)⁻ on the basis of ¹H nmr spectroscopy. The addition of one molar equivalent of HBF₄·Et₂O to the above reaction mixture produced an immediate colour change from dark orange to yellowish-orange. Removal of solvent followed by tlc (80% CH₂Cl₂ in hexane) produced an orange band consisting of Os₃(CO)₇(NCMe)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂Ph₂C₂) in 25% yield.

Preparation of Os₃(CO)₈(C₂H₄)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) (8): C₂H₄ gas (1 atm.) was bubbled through a CH₂Cl₂ solution of Os₃(CO)₈(NCMe)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) at room temperature for 0.5 h. Solvent was then removed by a fast stream of N₂. Purification of the resulting reaction mixture by tlc (80% CH₂Cl₂ in hexane) produced an orange band consisting of Os₃(CO)₈(C₂H₄)(Me₂C₂C(O)Me₂C₂) (8) in 30% yield.

Crystal structure determination of Os₃(CO)₇(NCMe)(Me₂C₂C(O)C₂Me₂C₂H₂):

Orange, multifaceted crystals were obtained by slow evaporation of CHCl₃/hexane solution at -50°.

Crystal data: C₂₀H₁₇NO₈Os₃, M=969.95, monoclinic, space group P2₁/n (alt. setting P2₁/c, No. 14), a=9.617 (1), b=18.473 (1), c=12.887 (1) Å,

TABLE 6—ATOMIC COORDINATES (×10⁴) AND EQUIVALENT ISOTROPIC DISPLACEMENT PARAMETERS (Å² × 10³)

	x	y	z	U(eq) [*]
Os(1)	3 043(1)	1 949(1)	1 781(1)	28(1)
Os(2)	2 797(1)	647(1)	2 708(1)	27(1)
Os(3)	261(1)	1 207(1)	1 906(1)	25(1)
N(1)	3 069(12)	1 613(6)	240(8)	40(4)
C(1)	3 132(15)	1 441(8)	-610(11)	45(5)
C(2)	3 259(24)	1 170(12)	-1 653(12)	84(9)
C(3)	4 920(16)	2 238(9)	1 710(11)	47(5)
O(1)	6 053(13)	2 423(8)	1 653(11)	84(6)
C(4)	2 477(14)	2 892(8)	1 431(9)	38(4)
O(2)	2 108(12)	3 488(5)	1 332(9)	58(4)
C(5)	-1 600(16)	882(7)	1 973(11)	43(5)
O(3)	-2 734(12)	682(7)	1 984(11)	75(5)
C(6)	372(13)	902(7)	498(11)	35(4)
O(4)	471(12)	726(6)	-372(7)	54(4)
C(7)	-270(13)	2 172(7)	1 590(6)	30(4)
O(5)	-670(11)	2 762(5)	1 398(8)	50(4)
C(8)	3 370(16)	236(8)	1 402(11)	45(5)
O(6)	3 715(15)	-11(7)	670(9)	82(5)
C(9)	4 237(16)	113(9)	3 365(11)	50(5)
O(7)	5 104(12)	-233(7)	3 773(11)	85(5)
O(10)	790(12)	143(7)	2 510(10)	33(4)
C(11)	1 087(13)	134(7)	3 565(10)	36(4)
C(12)	1 349(13)	845(7)	4 040(9)	33(4)
C(13)	433(14)	1 434(6)	3 594(9)	31(4)
C(14)	1 122(13)	2 138(7)	3 618(8)	30(4)
C(15)	2 668(14)	2 229(7)	3 444(9)	34(4)
C(16)	3 541(12)	1 599(7)	3 363(9)	29(4)
C(17)	1 898(15)	831(9)	5 164(10)	44(5)
C(18)	-930(15)	1 490(8)	4 140(11)	45(5)
O(8)	491(10)	2 709(5)	3 777(7)	43(3)
C(19)	3 211(16)	2 689(7)	3 859(12)	45(5)
C(20)	5 052(15)	1 632(10)	3 870(12)	53(5)

*Equivalent isotropic U defined as one third of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} tensor.

TABLE 7—ANISOTROPIC DISPLACEMENT PARAMETERS ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$)^a

	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{12}	U_{13}	U_{23}
Os(1)	30(1)	28(1)	25(1)	1(1)	3(1)	-6(1)
Os(2)	27(1)	27(1)	27(1)	3(1)	1(1)	4(1)
Os(3)	26(1)	24(1)	24(1)	0(1)	-3(1)	-1(1)
N(1)	51(7)	39(8)	32(6)	3(5)	8(5)	-11(5)
C(1)	47(9)	45(8)	43(9)	3(7)	10(7)	-14(7)
C(2)	116(18)	103(16)	36(9)	-20(9)	28(10)	-61(13)
C(3)	41(9)	64(10)	38(8)	9(7)	9(7)	-2(7)
O(1)	44(7)	111(11)	96(10)	12(8)	4(7)	-34(7)
C(4)	41(8)	48(9)	26(7)	-5(6)	3(6)	-20(7)
O(2)	77(8)	21(5)	77(8)	11(5)	10(6)	1(5)
C(5)	47(9)	33(7)	48(8)	-13(6)	-9(7)	-9(7)
O(3)	52(8)	76(8)	97(10)	-11(7)	8(7)	-24(7)
C(6)	25(6)	33(7)	46(8)	2(6)	-5(6)	5(5)
O(4)	66(7)	67(7)	29(5)	-9(5)	13(5)	-14(6)
C(7)	33(7)	28(7)	29(6)	-17(5)	-8(5)	-3(5)
O(5)	61(7)	32(5)	53(6)	2(4)	-8(5)	13(5)
C(8)	51(9)	42(8)	43(8)	-1(7)	10(7)	17(7)
O(6)	114(12)	81(9)	53(7)	-11(6)	31(7)	23(8)
C(9)	46(9)	65(10)	42(8)	6(7)	15(7)	6(8)
O(7)	51(7)	100(9)	99(10)	13(8)	-27(7)	47(7)
C(10)	24(6)	42(7)	32(7)	8(5)	-1(5)	0(5)
C(11)	30(7)	44(8)	36(7)	9(6)	5(6)	3(6)
C(12)	26(6)	43(7)	30(7)	-10(5)	6(5)	4(6)
C(13)	44(8)	28(6)	22(6)	-2(5)	-4(5)	8(6)
C(14)	29(7)	45(7)	16(6)	3(5)	0(5)	7(6)
C(15)	45(8)	41(7)	17(6)	-1(5)	5(5)	-6(6)
C(16)	26(6)	38(7)	21(6)	-1(5)	-6(5)	11(5)
C(17)	34(8)	69(10)	29(7)	2(7)	2(6)	1(7)
C(18)	43(8)	50(8)	42(8)	-9(6)	9(6)	3(7)
O(8)	42(6)	34(5)	52(6)	-12(4)	6(5)	8(4)
C(19)	52(9)	32(7)	52(9)	-9(6)	-1(7)	-8(6)
C(20)	34(8)	82(11)	42(8)	-7(8)	-11(7)	4(8)

^aThe anisotropic displacement exponent takes the form :

$$-2\pi^2(h^2 a^{*2} U_{11} + \dots + 2hk a^* b^* U_{12}).$$

$\beta = 92.71(1)^\circ$, $V = 2286.9 \text{ \AA}^3$ (by least-squares refinement on diffractometer angles from 40 automatically centred reflections, $\lambda = 0.71069 \text{ \AA}$), $D_c = 2.816 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $Z = 4$, $F(000) = 1744$. Orange, multifaceted block. Crystal dimensions (distance to faces from centre) : $0.116(010, 0\bar{1}0) \times 0.285(10\bar{1}, 10^1) \times 0.169(101, 10\bar{1}) \times 0.146(02\bar{1}, 021) \times 0.129(02\bar{1}, 021) \text{ mm}$, $\mu(\text{Mo-K}\alpha) = 166.80 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Data collection and processing : Stoe four-circle diffractometer, 24 step $\omega - \theta$ scan mode with ω scan width 0.04° , ω scan speed ranging from 0.5 to 2.0 s per step, graphite-monochromated Mo- K_α radiation; 4430 reflections measured ($5.0 < 2\theta < 50^\circ$, $+h, +k, \pm l$), 4026 unique [merging $R = 0.047$ after numerical absorption correction (maximum, minimum transmission factors 0.078, 0.037)], giving 3395 with $F < 4 \sigma(F)$. Three check reflections showed no significant variations during data collection.

Structure analysis and refinement : Centrosymmetric direct methods (Os atoms) followed by Fourier difference techniques. Blocked full-matrix least-squares refinement with all non-hydrogen atoms anisotropic, and methyl H in calculated positions (C-H 1.08 $\text{\AA}$ and H-C-H 109.5 $^\circ$) with a common isotropic thermal parameter of $0.08(2) \text{ \AA}^2$. The weighting scheme $w = 2.083/[\sigma^2(F) + 0.001 F_0^2]$, with

$\sigma(F_0)$ from counting statistics, gave satisfactory agreement analyses. The final R and R' values were 0.044 and 0.045. Highest peak in final difference map $3 \text{ e\AA}^{-3}$ close to the Os atom positions. Final fractional atomic coordinates and equivalent isotropic thermal parameters are listed in Table 6, anisotropic thermal parameters are listed in Table 7, and hydrogen atom coordinates in Table 8. Programs and computers used and sources of scattering factor data are given in ref. 17.

TABLE 8—H-ATOM COORDINATES ($\times 10^4$) AND ISOTROPIC DISPLACEMENT PARAMETERS ($\text{\AA}^2 \times 10^3$)

	x	y	z	U
H(21)	2 713	1 631	-1 986	82(34)
H(22)	2 659	7686	-1 813	82(34)
H(23)	4 262	1 121	-1 990	82(34)
H(171)	2 163	1 447	5 242	82(22)
H(172)	2 757	5555	5 466	82(22)
H(173)	986	768	5 593	82(22)
H(181)	-1 267	9778	3 808	82(22)
H(182)	-1 609	1 916	3 846	82(22)
H(183)	-966	1 464	4 975	82(22)
H(191)	4 300	2 998	3 692	82(22)
H(192)	3 078	3 138	4 650	82(22)
H(193)	2 620	3 322	3 335	82(22)
H(201)	5 730	1 189	3 690	82(22)
H(202)	4 767	1 590	4 668	82(22)
H(203)	5 585	2 139	3 758	82(22)

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References

1. B. F. G. JOHNSON, R. KHATTAR, J. LEWIS, P. R. RAITHEY and D. N. SMIT, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans*, 1988, 1421.
2. E. SAPPÀ, A. TIRIFICCHIO and P. BRAUNSTEIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1983, **83**, 203.
3. P. R. RAITHEY and J. M. ROSALES, *Adv. Inorg. Radiochem.*, 1985, **29**, 169.
4. F. W. B. EINSTEIN, K. G. TRACEY and D. SUTTON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 1631.
5. R. KHATTAR, B. F. G. JOHNSON, F. J. LAHOZ, J. LEWIS, P. R. RAITHEY and D. N. SMIT, *Organomet.*, to be submitted.
6. R. JACKSON, B. F. G. JOHNSON, J. LEWIS, P. R. RAITHEY and S. W. SANKEY, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1980, **193**, C1.
7. B. F. G. JOHNSON, R. KHATTAR, P. T. KAYE, F. J. LAHOZ, J. LEWIS and P. R. RAITHEY, *Organomet.*, to be submitted.
8. M. P. GÓMEZ-SAL, B. F. G. JOHNSON, R. A. KAMARUDIN, J. LEWIS and P. R. RAITHEY, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1985, 1622.
9. J. G. JEFFREY, B. F. G. JOHNSON, J. LEWIS, P. R. RAITHEY and D. A. WELCH, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1986, 318.
10. B. F. G. JOHNSON, J. LEWIS, J. A. LUNNISS, D. BRAGA and F. GREFIONI, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1988, 972.
11. A. J. DEEMING, S. HASSO and M. UNDERHILL, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 1614.
12. I. J. HART, J. C. JEFFERY, M. J. GROSSKOPFHOFF and F. G. A. STONE, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1988, 1867.
13. M. A. GALLOP, B. F. G. JOHNSON, R. KHATTAR, J. LEWIS and P. R. RAITHEY, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1990, **386**, 121.
14. P. A. DAWSON, B. F. G. JOHNSON, J. LEWIS, J. PUGA, P. R. RAITHEY and M. J. ROSALES, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.*, 1982, 233.
15. R. KHATTAR, B. F. G. JOHNSON, J. LEWIS, P. R. RAITHEY and M. J. ROSALES, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1990, 2167.
16. B. F. G. JOHNSON, J. LEWIS and D. A. PIFFARD, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1981, 407.
17. B. F. G. JOHNSON, J. LEWIS, P. R. RAITHEY, S. N. A. B. SAED-MUSTAFA, M. J. TAYLOR, K. WHITMIRE and W. CLEGG, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 2111.